

ULTRASOUND EFFECT ON THE BRAIN DEVELOPMENT IN MOUSE

A THESIS

*Submitted to the
Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore*

**For the Degree of
*DOCTOR OF SCIENCE (D.Sc)***

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NOVEMBER 2019**

Synopsis:

Brain is one of the most complex organs of the body, with an involved architecture in which different functions are localized in different structures. Differentiation of the latter takes place at different times and for different durations. This is particularly true of the development of the neocortex, which extends over a long time (Schull et. al. 1990).

A distinct feature of the developing brain is its long period of sensitivity. This undoubtedly reflects its architectural complexity, its long developmental period, the vulnerability of the undifferentiated neural cell as compared to the developed neuron, the fact that neuronal function is contingent upon position and that neuronal cells do not proliferate in the cortex but must migrate there, and the inability of the brain to replace lost neurons. Malformations of the central nervous system occur in the course of major organogenesis or during differentiation and growth of the brain mantle.

The sensitivity of the differentiating neural tissue to damage changes with age, but so too does its capacity to replace damaged cells. At any given time in development the probability of causing abnormalities and their severity change as the dose of the teratogenic agent changes. Moreover, since for the same dose damage can vary as a function of the time in development at which the insult occurs, malformations can also differ substantially in severity. With all the variable, the behavioural tests are extremely important as they follow observation of the intact organism, where invasive techniques are impracticable or more sensitive in detecting anomalous development and gives precise information concerning the action of toxic substance on the exposed organisms (Schull et. al. 1990).

Ultrasound has found increasing application in recent years, and has been extensively employed clinically to monitor the health and wellbeing of the developing fetus for nearly three decades (NCRP 1983). It is widely used in early pregnancy, as well as in all other stages of pregnancy to monitor fetal growth and development (Abdulla 1971, 1976, Campbell 1971). Such a large number of fetal exposures has been largely due to the perceived safety and medical benefits of this technology. The perceived safety of ultrasound considers that obvious deleterious effects have not been detected from the clinical use of ultrasound exposure (Stratmeyer & Fisher 1987)0 However experimental efforts to delineate the

bioeffects of ultrasound on in utero development have been inconclusive (Carstensen & Gates, O` Brien 1994).

Postnatal behavioural changes after prenatal exposure to ultrasound have been observed in a number of studies (Murai et. al 1975 a, b, Sikov et al 1977, Tarantal and Hendrickx 1989b, Norton et al 1991, Vorchees et al 1994, Hande & Uma Devi 1993, 1955). However, epidemiological and experimental data are controversial and insufficient in setting up a threshold level for the possible harmful effects of in utero exposure to diagnostic ultrasound. Also, no systematic study has been carried out to give conclusive evidence for or against the safety of diagnostic ultrasound and more information needs to be acquired. Therefore, the present investigation was planned to do a systematic study on the effect of diagnostic ultrasound on the postnatal brain development, its biochemistry and function after prenatal exposure to ultrasound at the organogenesis and fetal periods of laboratory mouse.

In all the experiments, a minimum of 15 pregnant Swiss albino mice of gestation days 10 to 18 post coitus (late organogenesis and foetal stages) from the colony maintained in our laboratory, were used and exposed to diagnostic levels of ultrasound (3.5 MHz, 65 mW, $I_{SPTP} = 1 \text{ W/cm}^2$, $I_{SATA} = 240 \text{ W/cm}^2$).

The following experiments were conducted

- i. Determination of gestational stage sensitivity to ultrasound exposure.
- ii. Effect of 10 min ultrasound exposure during the foetal period on the postnatal development and adult behaviour and hippocampal histology.
- iii. Effect of different durations of ultrasound exposure during the early fetal period on postnatal development and adult behaviour.

Experiment I

To select the sensitive stage (s) pregnant Swiss albino mice were exposed to diagnostic ultrasound for 30 min on any one day from day 10 to 18 of gestation. The animals were allowed to parturate and the offsprings were examined for the ultrasound induced effects on postnatal changes in physiological reflexes, mortality, body weight, body length, head length and head width upto 6 weeks of age. Tests to assess adult behaviour were conducted at 4 months of age. After the behavioural tests were completed, representative animals from each group were killed and the brain was dissected out. The hippocampal region of the brain was weighed and studied for changes in the biogenic amines. Ultrasound exposure

raised the maternal vaginal temperature to ~ 1.5°C above normal. Exposure at any day of gestation did not produce any change in the standard physiological reflexes like pinna detachment, eye opening and fur development. But postnatal mortality was significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) when compared to control in animals exposed on 13, 14 and 16 day of gestation. In the other groups the increase was nonsignificant compared to control. A transient reduction in body weight was observed at birth after exposure on 11, 12, 14 and 16 day of gestation when compared to the control. At 4th week of age of decrease in the body weight was seen only on 14 and 16 day p.c. exposed groups. Normal values were restored by 5th week of age in all the above groups. Exposure during later stages of pregnancy that is 17 and 18 days p.c. did not have any significant effect on body weight. Significant decrease in body length at birth was seen in all the exposed groups compared to control. In animals exposed on days 10 to 12 p.c recovery was seen after 2 to 3 weeks of age. But in the animals exposed on 14, 16, 17 and 18 days p.c. the body length remained significantly lesser than control throughout the postnatal growth period.

A significant decrease in the head length was observed at birth only in the groups exposed on 10, 13, 16 and 18 day of gestation. A significant decrease was noticed at 1-week of age in all the exposed groups and this effect persisted during the entire postnatal period upto 6 weeks of age. Head width of the offsprings at birth was significant decreased in all the exposed groups, except for those exposed on the 17 day of gestation. However, in the latter group the head width showed a significant decrease from 1st week onwards. This effect continued upto 6 weeks of age, in all the exposure groups. The increase in the growth retarded offsprings was significant only in animals exposed at 14th and 16th days p.c. In other groups the increase was nonsignificant.

Behavioural studies: The following behavioural tests were conducted at 4 month of age to assess the effect on adult brain function.

1. Locomotory activity was tested in the open field test.
2. Locomotory and exploratory activities were tested using dark/bright arena test.
3. Learning performance was assessed by the hole board test.
4. Learning and memory functions were tested in shuttle box.

The open field test showed highly significant decrease in the number of line crossings in all the exposure groups. In dark/bright arena test, the number of line crossings in the dark area in the offsprings exposed on days 11, 14, 15 or 16 days p.c. were more severely affected than the 10, 12, 13, 17 or 18 day p.c. exposed animals. A highly significant decrease was observed in the groups exposed on day 14 and 16 p.c. A significant increase in the number of line crossings in the bright area was observed in all the exposure groups. Similarly a significant decrease in the time spent in dark area was noticed in all the exposure groups.

Ultrasound exposure produced a significant change on learning and memory. A significant increase in the number of pokings was noticed on day one in the 12, 13, 14, 16 and 17 day p.c. exposed groups compared to control. This effect became more pronounced on the 2nd and 3rd days of testing in all the exposed groups compared to the respective controls.

In the shuttle box test, a significant decrease in avoidance reaction (mean of 5 days scores) was observed in all the exposures groups. The retest and the retention scores were also significantly lower in all the exposed groups compared to that of the control value.

The hippocampal weight showed a significant reduction in the 11, 12, 14, 15 and 16 day exposure groups. A nonsignificant decrease in the hippocampal weight was noticed in the remaining groups. A significant reduction in the dopamine content of hippocampus was noticed in the 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16 day exposure groups. However, the remaining groups the decrease was non significant when compared to control values. Non-adrenaline content was reduced significantly only in the 14, 15 and 16 day exposure groups. The serotonin level also decreased significantly in 10, 11, 14, 15 and 16 day exposure groups. However, a non significant change was observed in the metabolite of serotonin compared to the control group.

From these results it is found that ultrasound can induce changes on mouse development and brain function when given at the late organogenesis and foetal periods. However, day 14 and 16 p.c. during the foetal period appears to be the most sensitive to the ultrasound effect, in view of the number of different effects as well as severity of most of the observed effects when exposed on these gestation days.

Experiment II

On the basis of the above study, days 14 and 16 were selected to see if a shorter exposure (10 min) to diagnostic ultrasound can result in any detectable effects on postnatal development and adult brain function, as 10 min exposure is commonly used in our hospital for routine investigation.

Pregnant Swiss albino mice were exposed for 10 min to diagnostic ultrasound on day 14 or 16 of gestation and allowed to parturate. The offsprings were examined during early postnatal life for ultrasound induced changes in physiological reflexes, postnatal mortality, body weight, body length, head length and head width upto 6 weeks of age.

The effect on brain function was assessed when mice were 4 months old, by open field test and dark/bright arena test for locomotor and exploratory activity and by the hole board test and the shuttle box test for learning and memory as explained before. In order to see whether ultrasound exposure produced any histological changes in the hippocampal region of brain, coronal sections from the dorsal hippocampus of 10 animals from each group were taken and the number of neurons in different regions was counted under light microscope. Maternal vaginal temperature did not show any significant change compared to the normal values.

Ultrasound exposure did not produce any change in physiological reflexes. Postnatal mortality was also not significantly different from that of the control group.

A significant reduction in the body weight at birth compared to control weight was observed only in the animals exposed on day 14 p.c. This decrease in body weight continued upto 3rd week of age. The birth weight of animals exposed on day 16 p.c. was in the normal range. But they showed significantly lower than control body weight from 1st week to 4th week of age. However, all the exposed animals regained the control weight by the 4th week of age after which normal growth was resumed. The body length of the offspring in both the exposed groups showed a significant decrease at birth, which continued upto 5th week of age in the 16 day exposed group, while in the 14th day exposed group low body length continued even at 6 weeks of age.

Head length and head width was significantly reduced in both the exposed groups when compared to control values. This effect persisted during the entire postnatal period of 6 weeks of age.

Behavioural Studies : Animals were subjected to behavioural tests at 4 month of age assess the adult brain function.

Open field test showed a highly significant decrease in the number of life crossings in both the exposed groups compared to control. In the dark/bright arena test, the number of line crossings in dark area was significantly reduced in both the exposed groups. However, the line crossings in white area and time spent in dark area were significantly affected only in the 14th day exposed group. Though there was decrease in 16 day exposed group, it was non-significant compared to control.

A significant increase in the number of pokes in hole board test was noticed on day 1 of testing in the animals exposed on 14 day p.c. compared to control. This effect became pronounced on day three of testing in both the exposed group compared to control.

In the shuttle box test, the mean of 5 days scores, retest score and retention score were significantly lower in both the exposed groups compared to control values.

There was no gross structural change in the hippocampus in the exposed animals compared to control. However, the coronal sections of the dorsal hippocampus showed a decrease in the number of neurons in the CA3 and CA4 regions in the 14 day exposed animals. But the decrease was significant only in the CA3 region.

Experiment III

The results of the above experiments showed that day 14 p.c. is particularly sensitive to ultrasound induced changes and even a short exposure of 10 min to diagnostic ultrasound during this stage produced significant impairment of brain function. Earlier, Hande *et al.*(1993) had found that ultrasound exposure for 10 min on 14.5 day p.c. caused significant change in anxiolytic activity and latency in learning behaviour. Therefore, this experiment was planned to see if the effects of ultrasound exposure at 14.5 day of mouse gestation increase with the increase in the exposure time and whether the effects on brain function persist at later ages.

Pregnant Swiss albino mice were exposed to diagnostic ultrasound for 10, 20 or 30 min on day 14.5 of gestation and allowed to parturate. The off springs were

observed for changes in physiological reflexes (such as pinna detachment, opening on eyes and development of fur) and postnatal mortality upto 6 weeks of age. Changes in the adult brain function was assessed by open field test and dark/bright arena test for locomotor and exploratory activity and hole board test and conditioned avoidance test for learning and memory at 4 months age.

The vaginal temperature of mother increased with duration of ultrasound, reaching a maximum temperature of 1.3 above normal for 30 min exposure. Physiological markers did not show any change from normal in any of the ultrasound exposed groups. Postnatal survival was also affected significantly in any of the ultrasound exposed groups compared to control.

Behavioural studies at 4 month of age showed significant change in brain function. The open field test showed a significant decrease in line crossings even after 10 min exposure, which further decreased significantly with increase in time of exposure to 10 min. However, an increase in the exposure time to 30 min did not produce any noticeable change over that after 20 min exposure. In dark/bright arena test the line crossings in the dark area was significantly reduced after 10 min of ultrasound exposure compared to the control. However, an increase in the time of exposure to 20 or 30 min did not result in any further change in this effect. The line crossings in bright area were not affected significantly by 10 or 20 min exposure, but exposure for 30 min resulted in a significant increase in this parameter. Similarly, a significant decrease in the time spent in the dark area was seen only after 30 min exposure. Exposure for 10 or 20 min produced a non-significant decrease in this effect.

A 10 min exposure significantly increased the number of poking in the hole board test on all 3-days of testing. Increase in exposure time to 20 min did not produce any noticeable change in this parameter from that after 10 min exposure. However, the number of pokings on the third day was significantly higher after a 30 min exposure compared to 10 and 20 min exposures.

The avoidance reaction (mean of 5-day scores) showed a significant decrease from control after 10 min ultrasound exposure. Exposure for 20 min or 30 min did not change this effect significantly from that of 10 min exposure. The retest score was significantly lower than control after 10 min exposure and further decreased when duration of exposure was increased to 20 min. However 30 min exposure produced only a small non-significant decrease in the retest score compared to 20 min exposure.

Behavioural studies at 1 year of age: The number of line crossings in the open field test showed significant decrease after 10 and 20 min of ultrasound exposure. This effect was further pronounced in increase in time of exposure to 30 min over the lower exposures. In dark/bright arena test the number of line crossings in dark area was significantly reduced after 10 and 20 min exposures compared to control and increase in time of exposure to 30 min further enhanced this effect. The time spent in the dark area showed only a slight nonsignificant decrease after 10 min exposure, but exposure to 20 to 30 min enhanced this effect to significant levels. The line crossings in the bright area were not significantly affected by 10 or 20 min exposure, but showed a significant increase after exposure to 30 min.

A 10 min exposure significantly increased the number of poking in the hole board test on all the 3 days of testing compared to control values. An increase in exposure time to 20 or 30 min did not result in any noticeable change over that of 10 min exposure. Similarly in the conditioned avoidance test the mean of 5 days scores showed a significant decrease after 10 min of ultrasound exposure, but increase in exposure time to 20 or 30 min did not produce any significant change in this effect over 10 min of exposure. The retest score also showed a similar response but retention score showed an enhancement of effect by increasing exposure time for 20 to 30 min.

Based on the above study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Intrauterine exposure to diagnostic ultrasound for 30 min during the late organogenesis and most of the foetal period can result in increased postnatal mortality, temporary growth retardation and changes in adult behaviour in mouse.
2. The behavioural changes after ultrasound exposure seem to be mediated through the biogenic amines in the brain.
3. Though most of the late organogenesis and early foetal development stages are sensitive to the ultrasound effect on postnatal development and adult behaviour, day 14 and 16 p.c. appears to be particularly vulnerable to these effects; day 14 p.c. showed the maximum sensitivity.
4. Even a short exposure of 10 min to diagnostic ultrasound during the most sensitive period, i.e. 14 day p.c. is sufficient to produce significant changes

in the postnatal development, adult brain function and the hippocampal neurons.

5. Day 14.5 p.c. also appears to be equally sensitive to ultrasound induced behavioural changes, though less sensitive to postnatal mortality. No dose (exposure time) dependent increase in effect could be observed within the range of exposure time, 10 min to 30 min, used in this study.
6. Exposure of the early foetal brain can lead to permanent neuro physiological changes in mouse, as evidenced from the behavioural impairment at 1 year of age after exposure at 14.5 day p.c.
7. Even though ultrasound is generally considered safer than x-rays, the present study indicates that exposure at certain stages of prenatal brain development can produce long lasting neuro physiological changes, even in the absence of externally detectable abnormalities.
8. However extrapolation from the mouse experiments to humans has to wait further data from exposures at comparable development phase in the two species and also should take into consideration other factors resulting from differences in the morphological dimensions between the abdomens of humans and mouse.